

Robust and Resilient GNSS Synchronization of LEO Satellites for Space-based Aircraft Multilateration

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Abstract— This paper aims at developing a robust and resilient synchronization framework for Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellites based on the combination of GNSS and Precision Time Protocol (PTP) via inter-satellite link. The satellite synchronization is needed to enable precise aircraft tracking in areas without radar coverage, by leveraging Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) signals and advanced localization algorithms, exploiting Time Of Arrival (TOA), Frequency Of Arrival (FOA), and Angle Of Arrival (AOA). An Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) corrects onboard clock errors in real time, while detecting and mitigating anomalies or cyber-attacks like GNSS jamming, spoofing or denial of service. Nanosecond accuracy under nominal and disrupted conditions is obtained, significantly enhancing safety and reliability of the tracking system.

Keywords—ADS-B, Multilateration, AOA, FOA, TOA, GNSS, PTP, Synchronization, LEO satellite

I. INTRODUCTION

Air traffic control has traditionally relied on Secondary Surveillance Radar (SSR) and procedural methods in regions without radar coverage. Recently, Automatic Dependent Surveillance-Broadcast (ADS-B) has emerged as a critical surveillance method, transmitting aircraft identity and position data. Space-Based ADS-B (SB ADS-B) enhances this capability by enabling communication with satellites, particularly in remote and oceanic areas where ground-based stations are impractical. This advancement not only reduces aircraft separation but also improves airspace efficiency by allowing more direct routes and better access to optimal altitudes, leading to decreased greenhouse gas emissions.

However, ADS-B transmissions are susceptible to natural or intentional disruptions, raising concerns about their integrity; Multilateration (MLAT) offers a promising solution to these challenges, enabling passive aircraft location without reliance on GNSS or ground-based radars. MLAT has demonstrated its effectiveness in airport surveillance and en-route operations. The integration of ADS-B and MLAT, referred to as composite surveillance, provides an alternative to the traditional combination of ADS-B and SSR Mode S. With the advent of space-based ADS-B (SB ADS-B) systems, the SATERA project [1] aims at exploring the feasibility of implementing composite surveillance in the space domain, ensuring reliable coverage in regions where conventional systems are inoperable.

SATERA proposes the deployment of a Low Earth Orbit (LEO) satellite constellation able to receive the ADS-B

messages transmitted by the aircraft and using these signals to localize the aircraft exploiting localization algorithms based on the Time Of Arrival (TOA) of the signals measured from at least four satellites. Moreover, SATERA proposes additional signal measurements such as Angle Of Arrival (AOA) and Frequency Of Arrival (FOA) to improve the localization performance.

Fig. 1. SATERA System description.

Fig. 1 shows the general description of the SATERA project: satellites in LEO orbits receive ADS-B messages and measure their TOA, FOA and AOA. These measurements are transferred together with the received messages to a Ground Station (GS) and then reach the Central Processing Station (CPS). Focusing on TOA measurements, if the CPS receives at least four TOAs for the same message it can independently compute the aircraft position by exploiting localization techniques. Follows that the satellites should share a common reference time, because a bias on a TOA directly affects the localization accuracy of the system, and a precise, robust, and reliable synchronization procedure becomes mandatory.

Moreover, this procedure needs to have low complexity (in terms of hardware, power consumption, dimension etc.), as it is to be installed on small LEO satellites. A GNSS receiver onboard the satellite is typically a simple solution for both satellite positioning and time synchronization [1][2] However, only having GNSS as synchronization method represents a single point of failure; it makes the system vulnerable to attacks or GNSS failures. In SATERA it is proposed to add another synchronization channel, to improve overall reliability and robustness. SATERA will introduce the

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use of Precise Time Protocol (PTP) [3] over Inter-Satellite Link (ISL) to obtain the required redundancy. Precise Time Protocol is a network-based synchronization protocol defined by IEEE. It is designed to achieve high-precision clock synchronization across distributed systems by exchanging timestamped messages, while compensating for delays introduced by network and hardware.

The PTP over ISLs, together with the onboard GNSS and PTP measurements will be used to estimate the onboard clock bias (and drift) by exploiting an ad-hoc Extended Kalman Filter [4]. Moreover, a detection mechanism to detect GNSS failures or attacks and automatically discard the erroneous measurements, maintaining a high level of synchronization accuracy, will also be proposed and evaluated.

This paper is organized as follows: Section II introduces the architecture of the proposed synchronization procedure, presents the clock model and the tracking algorithm used to correct errors and detect failures; Section III discusses the performance of the system in presence of different types of faults; Section IV concludes the paper.

II. SATERA SYNCHRONIZATION ALGORITHM

The architecture of the proposed solution is illustrated in Fig. 2. Each satellite in the SATERA LEO constellation is equipped with a stable clock referred to the Coordinated Universal Time (UTC). An Oven Controlled Crystal Oscillator (OCXO) is proposed in SATERA due to the importance of the synchronization error when computing the aircraft position. The satellites acquire a time measurement from GNSS every second to maintain its synchronization with the UTC time.

A ground station, equipped with an independent master clock (an atomic clock, in nominal condition synchronized with the UTC and capable of maintaining long term stability during the GNSS outage and or failures), serves as additional secure synchronization source. This ground station communicates with the SATERA satellites and performs time synchronization via PTP. Furthermore, ISLs enable the satellites to perform additional PTP synchronizations among themselves, propagating the clock information across the entire constellation, also where the ground station is not reachable.

The PTP synchronization is performed at a reduced time rate to preliminary take into account the network load, assumed to occur every 10 seconds.

Moreover, a clock model and the tracking algorithm provide a framework for estimating the clock behaviour (bias and drift) with time. The clock model represents the behaviour of oscillatory processes considering systematic and random errors, while the tracking algorithm ensures real-time synchronization and correction of deviation using time related measurements. They are defined in the following subsections.

Fig. 2. SATERA satellite synchronization process.

A. Clock model

A clock generates an oscillatory signal whose ideal output is represented as:

$$v(t) = v_0 \sin(2\pi f_0 t) \quad (1)$$

However, real clocks exhibit deviations due to imperfections in the oscillator. Taking this into account, we can rewrite (1) as:

$$v(t) = v_0 \sin(2\pi f_0 t + \phi(t)) \quad (2)$$

where $\phi(t)$ is the phase deviation, representing the cumulative effects of frequency errors and noise. Instead of the actual frequency $f(t)$, the deviation from the nominal frequency f_0 , $y(t)$, is usually used, it is expressed as:

$$y(t) = \frac{f(t) - f_0}{f_0} \quad (3)$$

and the time deviation with respect to the time interval is given by:

$$x(t) = \int_0^t y(t) dt \quad (4)$$

The time deviation originates from two main error components: systematic fluctuations and random fluctuations. Systematic fluctuations primarily cause long-term divergence from nominal time and frequency and can be approximated as:

$$x_{sys}(t) = x(0) + y(0)t + 0.5Dt^2 \quad (5)$$

where, $x(0)$ is the initial time offset, $y(0)$ is the initial frequency deviation offset, and D represents the frequency drift caused by factors like aging or production tolerances. Moreover, random fluctuations dominate short-term behaviour and are given by five noise types: White Phase Modulation (WPM), Flicker Phase Modulation (FPM), White Frequency Modulation (WFM), Flicker Frequency Modulation (FFM), and Random Walk Frequency Modulation (RWFM).

A Stochastic Differential Equation (SDE) model for the clock, combining systematic deviations (time offset, frequency offset, and drift) with key random components (WFM and RWFM), that effectively captures the dynamic behaviour of an oscillator is given in [5][6]. The following iterative solution for this model can be derived:

$$\begin{cases} x_1(t_{k+1}) = x_1(t_k) + (x_2(t_k) + \mu_1)\tau + \mu_2 \frac{\tau^2}{2} + K_{k,1} \\ x_2(t_{k+1}) = x_2(t_k) + \mu_2\tau + K_{k,2} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Where $K_k = [K_{k,1}, K_{k,2}]^T$ is a zero mean, Gaussian distributed noise term with covariance matrix equal to:

$$Q = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1^2\tau + \sigma_2^2 \frac{\tau^3}{3} & \sigma_2^2 \frac{\tau^2}{2} \\ \sigma_2^2 \frac{\tau^2}{2} & \sigma_2^2\tau \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

In the equations, x_1 represents the time deviation, while the frequency deviation $y(t)$ is given by \dot{x}_1 . The term x_2 corresponds to a component of the clock frequency deviation, often referred to as a random walk component. The constants σ_1 and σ_2 are called diffusion coefficients and can be derived by the clock Allan standard deviation with the procedures derived in [7] for different types of clocks. Finally, μ_1 and μ_2 represents the systematic fluctuations of the clock.

In matrix notation the clock model becomes:

$$x(t_{k+1}) = Fx(t_k) + B_\tau m + K_k \quad (8)$$

where:

$$\begin{aligned} x(t_k) &= \begin{bmatrix} x_1(t_k) \\ x_2(t_k) \end{bmatrix} & F &= \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \tau \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \\ B_\tau &= \begin{bmatrix} \tau & \frac{\tau}{2} \\ 0 & \tau \end{bmatrix} & m_\tau &= \begin{bmatrix} \mu_1 \\ \mu_2 \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

These equations can be used to track the clock bias and frequency deviations with respect to a reference time frame, if bias and/or frequency deviation measurements are available.

B. Clock bias Measurements

As described in Section II, Each satellite retrieves two different time measurements: from the onboard GNSS receiver and from the PTP ISLs network. Both these measurements refer to the clock bias and can be considered affected by an Additive White Gaussian Noise (AWGN), representing the measurement error: Δt_G is the measured bias of the onboard GNSS receiver, and Δt_N the measurement bias exploiting the PTP over ISLs network.

Furthermore, the measurement additive error is considered having a zero mean and the following standard deviations : $\sigma_G = 15$ ns (e.g. the Galileo nominal accuracy, 95% - 2σ , is 30 ns [8][9] also if usually it is lower as reported in [16]) and $\sigma_N = 500$ ns [10][11] for Δt_G and Δt_N respectively.

C. Clock tracking and fault detection

The proposed models were used to develop an Extended Kalman Filter (EKF) for tracking and estimating the clock parameters. In particular the filter state at time t_k : $x(t_k)$, is specified in Equation (9); the transition matrix F is outlined in Equation (9); the process noise covariance matrix Q , is provided in Equation (7).

Concerning the measurement $z(t_k)$, it can be composed of one or two elements depending on the available measurements at time t_k :

$$\begin{aligned} z(t_k) &= \begin{bmatrix} \Delta t_G(t_k) \\ \Delta t_N(t_k) \end{bmatrix} \\ z(t_k) &= [\Delta t_G(t_k)] \\ z(t_k) &= [\Delta t_N(t_k)] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

having the following measurement matrices (C_k), and measurement error covariance matrices (R_k):

$$C_k = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 1 & 0 \end{bmatrix}, C_k = [1 \ 0], C_k = [1 \ 0] \quad (11)$$

$$R_k = \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_G^2 & 0 \\ 0 & \sigma_N^2 \end{bmatrix}, R_k = [\sigma_G^2], R_k = [\sigma_N^2] \quad (12)$$

For each iteration, the EKF computes the filter gain G_k , the estimated state and the predicted state for the following steps $x^P(t_{k+1})$, with the relative covariance matrices P_k and P_k^P .

With this formulation the EKF can exploit the measurements coming from GNSS and PTP with different time rate and accuracy.

Moreover, in SATERA we propose to test the innovation of the EKF to detect GNSS faults or attacks. In fact, the innovation vector, defined as $I_k = z(t_k) - Fx^P(t_{k-1})$, contains the difference between expected and real measurements at time k and, if there is a fault affecting the real measurement $z(t_k)$ (i.e.: a bias on the GNSS measurements), it can be detected observing the relative innovation vector component [12]. In the case of a GNSS fault, it is necessary to evaluate the first component of I_k .

The innovation vector covariance matrix is given by:

$$R_k + FP_k^P F^T \quad (13)$$

and the following test can be done to detect an outlier in the GNSS measurements:

$$|I_k(1)| \leq k\sqrt{R_k(1,1)} \quad (14)$$

where k is a scalar to fix the probability of false alarm. Considering that $I_k(1)$ is Gaussian distributed with variance $R_k(1,1)$, hereafter, the k value is set to 2.5 to obtain a probability of false alarm of the order of 0.01.

If the absolute value of the innovation element is bigger than the threshold values, the measurement is considered an outlier (due to failure or attack) and discarded. An alarm is also raised. Fig. 3 shows all the details of the proposed algorithm.

Input:	
$x(t_k)$: Clock state vector at time t_k	
$P(t_k)$: State covariance matrix at time T_k	
$P^p(t_k)$: Prediction covariance matrix at time T_k	
F : Transition matrix as defined in (9)	
Q : process noise covariance matrix as derived in (7)	
C_k : observation matrix as defined in (11)	
R_k : measurement error covariance as defined in (12)	
$z(t_k)$: observation vector at time t_k as defined in (10)	
Output:	
$x(t_{k+1})$: clock state vector at time t_{k+1}	
$P(t_{k+1})$: state covariance matrix at time t_{k+1}	
Alarms	
1. Prediction	Predict the state for the time instant t_{k+1} : $x^p(t_{k+1}) = Fx(t_k)$; Predict the state covariance matrix: $P^p(t_{k+1}) = FP(t_k)F^T + Q$
2. Innovation test	Compute the innovation: $I_{k+1} = z(t_{k+1}) - Fx^p(t_{k+1})$ Compute the innovation covariance matrix: $R_{k+1} + FP_{k+1}^pF^T$ Compute the test on the GNSS: $ I_{k+1}(1) \leq k\sqrt{R_k(1,1)}$ If innovation > threshold \rightarrow raise alarm
3. Update	If the alarm is raised, update only with PTP Compute Kalman gain: $G_{k+1} = P_{k+1}^p C_{k+1} (R_{k+1} + FP_{k+1}^p F^T)$ Update the clock state vector: $x(t_{k+1}) = x^p(t_{k+1}) + G_{k+1} I_{k+1,k}$ Update the state covariance matrix: $P(t_{k+1}) = (1 - G_{k+1} F) P_{k+1}^p$

Fig. 3. SATERA satellite synchronization algorithm.

III. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

The proposed algorithm was evaluated by simulating an OCXO clock for 80000 seconds, and tracking its bias and drift with the algorithm reported in Fig. 3. The parameters σ_1 and σ_2 was computed as in [7] considering typical values for the Allan deviation of an OCXO [13][14][15].

The r.m.s. error of the clock estimated bias for each time epoch was computed using 100 Montecarlo runs for each epoch. Moreover, four different types of failures/attacks were simulated and evaluated; in all cases the failure/attack always starts at time 50000 (sec.) and ends at time 60000 and is highlighted in yellow in the figures.

The parameters used for the simulation and the evaluation results are summarized in TABLE I.

Starting from the most probable failure/attack, the Denial of Service (DoS) attack or the GNSS blockage, it was simulated by removing all GNSS measurements between time 50000 sec and time 60000 sec. An example of the results (measurements, real clock bias behaviour and estimated bias) is shown in Fig. 4. During the attack the onboard clock uses only the PTP measurements and the synchronization performance remains high during all the attack.

TABLE I. SIMULATION PARAMETERS

Parameter	Value
# Montecarlo runs	100
GNSS error: σ_{GNSS}	15 ns – considering GNSS time accuracy 30 ns (95%) [16]
NET error: σ_{NET}	500 ns [10][11]
GNSS renewal time	1 sec
NET renewal time	10 sec
Clock: σ_1	$4.47 \cdot 10^{-13}$ sec*
Clock: σ_2	$5.47 \cdot 10^{-14}$ Hz*
k	2.5 (to set the probability of false alarm to 0.01)

*typical value for an OCXO [13][14][15] as computed in [7]

Fig. 4. Simulation of DoS attack on GNSS.

Moreover, less probable types of failures and attack were also analysed. A bias step in the GNSS measurements was simulated to emulate a possible failure or attack affecting the onboard GNSS receiver (for example this can be the effect of a spoofer on the PVT estimation of the onboard GNSS receiver). In this case, the GNSS measurements between time 50000 sec and time 60000 sec. were affected from a bias of 100 or 500 nanoseconds. An example of the results (measurements, real clock bias behaviour and estimated bias, for a bias of 500 ns) is shown in Fig. 5.

Note that in this case the algorithm clearly detects the step in the GNSS measurements and discards the biased measurements.

Fig. 5. Simulation of bias step in GNSS measurement.

Also, the case of a slow changing bias (a bias ramp) in the GNSS measurement was simulated to emulate a smarter spoofer affecting the satellite. GNSS measurements between time 50000 sec and time 60000 sec were affected by a bias ramp with a ramp coefficient of 10^{-10} sec/sec. An example

of the results is shown in Fig. 6. Note that also in this case the algorithm detects the step in the GNSS measurements and discards the biased measurements.

Fig. 6. Simulation of bias ramp.

Last, far jammer or the effect of solar or ionospheric storms on the GNSS receiver on board can cause a reduction of the GNSS performance. This condition was simulated by improving the noise of the GNSS measurements during the attack (see Fig. 7).

Fig. 7. Simulation of reduced measurement accuracy.

A comparison of the results for all the previous cases is reported in Fig. 8, Fig. 9 and TABLE II. Fig. 8 shows the r.m.s. errors in the various cases, Fig. 9 shows the alarm probability before, during and after the attack and TABLE II shows a summary of the results showing the r.m.s. that can be obtained with the proposed algorithm in nominal condition or after 10/100/1000 seconds of disruption.

It can be noted that the most harmful cases are noise improvement and the bias step, but they are also easy to detect. In general, all the failures are detected, and it is possible to assume that the system can continue to work under

attack or fault thanks to the mitigation effects of the detector introduced in the EKF.

TABLE II. RMS RESULTS UNDER NOMINAL AND ATTACK CONDITIONS.

Disruption Type	RMS performance (ns)				
	Nominal	Under Attack 10 sec	Under Attack 100 sec	Under Attack 1000 sec	Under Attack Max
DOS	<1	<1	<1	2.36	29.10
STEP 100 ns	<1	<1	<1	2.41	100.96
STEP 500 ns	<1	<1	<1	2.57	23.40
RAMP	<1	<1	4.25	11.46	37.30
NOISESTEP 500 ns	<1	<1	<1	3.79	79.42
NOISE STEP 100 ns	<1	<1	1.12	4.09	21.63

Fig. 8. RMS error in different cases.

Fig. 9. Alarm probability.

Fig. 9 also shows that in some cases (noise500 and step100) the probability of detection slowly decreases during the attack/fault and that, after its end, some time is needed to restore the nominal condition. This happens because the instant in which the disruption ends is seen by the detector as a new deviation from normal behaviour. In any case, this will not affect the general performance during the first seconds of failure. In fact, TABLE II shows that also considering 1000 seconds (more than 15 minutes) of continuous disruption, the maximum estimation error of the onboard clock bias is of the order of 10 nanoseconds, and during the 15 minutes there are continuous alarms, that can be used to start a recovery action by the SATERA system.

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a resilient synchronization framework for LEO satellites based on GNSS and packet-based PTP over ISLs, within the SATERA project, addressing the critical need for reliable time synchronization in space-based multilateration systems. The proposed architecture ensures high accuracy and GNSS fault tolerance, maintaining synchronization performance below 5 ns r.m.s., even in case of long-lasting failures or attacks on the GNSS system; it remains resilient in nearly all scenarios, including continuous failures or attacks lasting up to 100 ns.

Moreover, it is able to generate alarm within the system to promptly notify the users. In particular, in the most probable failure scenarios, that are the GNSS DOS (also due to signal interruption) and the GNSS performance reduction, the proposed algorithm guarantees high probability of failure detection and high synchronization accuracy.

Finally, it must be noted that the main aim of this paper is only to evaluate the feasibility of a resilience algorithm to reduce the risk of GNSS failures. On the other hand, the use of ISLs-PTP may introduce other potential single points of failure related to ground/satellite communication for the PTP synchronization and possible network issues such as a more complex routing algorithm, high network load and higher power consumption. Concerning the possible points of failure in the network, they can be mitigated by the classical access protection for the CPS and authentication/encryption schemes for the network. This is out of scope of this paper but will be addressed later in the project. Concerning the PTP network load, it was preliminary taken into account in the paper setting a low rate of PTP measurements (every 10 sec). Moreover, two other important mitigations can be considered: (1) the SATERA localization algorithms may work also with a local (not worldwide) synchronization of the satellite, and this can also reduce the load of the PTP time distribution (for example synchronizing sub-networks of satellites), (2) the update rate of the PTP synchronization can be adaptive and its measurement rate can be reduced when the system does not produce alarms. Future works will focus on optimizing PTP to balance time accuracy, cost and network efficiency.

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